

A NEW SYSTEM FOR RECORDING
UNSTABLE AERODYNAMIC PHENOMENA
IN
NAVSWC HYPERVELOCITY WIND TUNNEL #9.

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Abstract

Hypervelocity Wind Tunnel #9, located at the Naval Surface Warfare Center (NAVSWC) in Silver Spring, MD, is a blow down wind tunnel which operates at Mach numbers 8, 10, and 14. Since it became operational in 1976, Tunnel 9 has continuously provided advanced technology for tests supporting strategically vital programs for the Department of Defense, and NASA. Over the past several years test programs in Tunnel 9 have begun to investigate transient aerodynamic phenomena as well as the typical steady state events. The desire to better quantify transient events has led to the procurement of a 20,000,000 sample/sec data acquisition system. The new system, High Speed Data Acquisition and Recording Equipment, (HSDARE), has been operational since June, 1990, and is available for Tunnel 9 tests requiring high temporal resolution.

Introduction

The data acquisition facility at Tunnel 9 is capable of acquiring data from 350 model resident standard speed sensors and 20 model resident high speed sensors. The facility is comprised of three DARE (Data Acquisition and Recording Equipment) systems. Two of the systems, DARE 6 and DARE 8, form the standard speed recording platform. The other system, HSDARE, records transient events. An analog tape recorder, Honeywell 101, is also part of the facility, but its use has been preempted by the arrival of the new HSDARE.

In 1986 DARE 6 became the primary data acquisition system for Tunnel 9. It was purchased from Cyber Systems, Inc. of Anaheim, CA. DARE 6 replaced an outdated system, DARE 5, which was comprised of such antiquated technology as paper tape readers and teletypes. DARE 6 brought with it a computerized approach to data acquisition and is more characteristic of the systems available today. Its 256 channels and

total sampling throughput of 200,000 samples per second have proven adequate for test programs up until now.

Soon after the procurement of DARE 6 another system, DARE 8, was purchased from Cyber Systems, Inc. Until 1991 DARE 8 was used as the primary data acquisition system for Hypervelocity Tunnels 8 and 8A at NAVSWC. It is an exact duplicate of DARE 6 with the exception of number of channels. Both DARE 8 and DARE 6 are completely software and hardware compatible.

This year DARE 8 has been joined with DARE 6 to support Tunnel 9 testing. Together the two systems are capable of acquiring data from 350 model resident sensors and 98 tunnel condition sensors mounted outside of the model. A further upgrade of the systems is scheduled for June - August 1992. That upgrade will make the facility capable of acquiring data from 400 model sensors and 112 tunnel condition sensors.

In Tunnel 9 each sensor is typically sampled and recorded by a data system 250 to 1000 times per second. Each of Tunnel 9's standard speed data acquisition systems (DARE 8 and DARE 6) have a single analog to digital converter. The analog to digital converter in each system is able to digitize analog signals 200,000 times per second. Although 200,000 samples per second is moderately high, it represents the total throughput of a DARE system. Two hundred thousand is the sampling budget. Each sensor which is sampled uses up a portion of the sampling budget. In order to sample transducers at high rates a sacrifice must be made in the number of sensors sampled. For example, to achieve 40,000 samples per second per gauge the sampling budget of DARE 6 or DARE 8 runs out at five gauges.

Over the past few years significant interest has surfaced concerning unstable aerodynamic phenomena. In Tunnel 9 tests unstable aerodynamic phenomena are defined as events which are not well characterized and which

change state drastically in a period of time shorter than 50 microseconds. Some examples of unstable aerodynamic phenomena are shock waves inside of an inlet, turbulent flow inside of a boundary layer, organ pipe effects in short pressure tubing, and pressure waves originating from an explosive mechanism such as that used in a recent Army HEDI shroud separation test.

In order to resolve events lasting less than 50 μ Sec. it is necessary to satisfy the Nyquist criteria and sample each sensor at a rate higher than 40,000 times per second. Using DARE 8 and DARE 6 to resolve transient aerodynamic phenomena is not feasible. At 40,000 samples per second a total of 10 gauges (5 sampled by DARE 6 @ 40,000 samples/second/gauge, 200,000 total, and 5 sampled by DARE 8 @ 40,000 samples/second/gauge, 200,000 total) would expend the sampling budget of both systems. Only 10 sensors could be sampled per wind tunnel run. Most test matrices require data acquisition from hundreds of sensors. The inconsistency between the amount and speed of data acquisition required and amount and speed of data acquisition available is obvious. Using the standard speed systems to sample limited numbers of gauges at high rates is fruitless. Although possible, it would be an extreme mismanagement of resources, and would greatly reduce the number of "steady state" gauges sampled.

The HSDARE was purchased to provide transient signal acquisition while maintaining the capability to sample high quantities of standard speed sensors. The HSDARE samples signals one million times per second and resolves signals with bandwidths up to 100 KHz. The HSDARE provides the transient data acquisition function of the Tunnel 9 data acquisition facility, and it allows DARE 8 and DARE 6 to continue their original function of acquiring "steady state" signals.

Background

Before the HSDARE arrived, a Honeywell 101 analog tape recorder was used in conjunction with one of the DARE systems to record transient signals. An upsampling system was constructed using the two systems. An upsampling system is one which extends the temporal resolution of an incoming signal by allowing the signal to be sampled more often than it would be in real time. Data would be recorded on the Honeywell 101 in

real time, and after the run the data would be played back slowly to the DARE system and digitized. Figure 1 shows a schematic of the system.

Figure 1 Upsampling System Block Diagram.

In Figure 1 two functional blocks are represented. The first, the upsampler, is actually the Honeywell 101. The second, the analog to digital converter, is the DARE system used in the playback phase. A continuous time signal $x(t)$ is recorded by the Honeywell 101 in real time. After the run, the signal recorded by the Honeywell 101 is played back to the input side of the DARE system. The playback is performed at 1/128th of the actual recording speed. The signal played back is denoted $x(t)'$ since it is still a continuous time signal. The signal $x(t)'$ is digitized by the DARE system (A to D), and the outcome is $x[n]$, the discrete time representation of the signal $x(t)$ upsampled. In effect the signal $x(t)$ is recorded by the DARE system at 128 times the sampling rate that the DARE system could provide by itself.

In order to provide correlation between data taken in real time by the DARE system from steady state gauges and data post processed by the DARE system from the Honeywell 101 it was necessary to record the transient signals with the DARE system in real time also. Figure 2 shows a diagram of the arrangement.

Signals originating in the wind tunnel model are amplified by a buffer amplifier and routed to the Honeywell 101 in real time. The same signals are amplified by a DARE system amplifier and recorded in real time also. After the wind tunnel run, the top "switch" is closed and the real time Honeywell 101 data are played back to the DARE system through a buffer amplifier. The arrangement of Figure 2 was used for a particle separator flow field calibration in 1988, and for the

measurement of pressure fluctuations in the Tunnel 9 flow in 1982.

Figure 2 Connection of DARE and Honeywell 101

During the 1982 measurement of pressure fluctuations in Tunnel 9 a single pressure transducer was recorded with the Honeywell 101 at 120 inches per second (ips) tape speed. Next it was played back to the DARE 5 (the system that preceded DARE 6). The DARE 5 digitizing speed was 2,000 samples per second. The data recorded by the Honeywell 101 were played back to the DARE 5 at a speed of 0.937 ips. The result was a sampling rate of 256,000 samples per second.

Due to the sampling of an analog signal below its Nyquist rate aliasing. The Nyquist rate corresponds to the highest frequency component of a signal multiplied by two. In the pressure fluctuation test the effective sampling rate was 256,000 samples per second. The folding frequency, one half of the nyquist rate, was therefore 128,000 Hz. Since the folding frequency was 128,000 Hz it is reasonable to assume that the setup of Figure 2 has unlimited resolution of signals up to 128,000 Hz. However, the output of the Honeywell 101 is low pass filtered at 80 KHz, therefore no signals above 80 KHz were present.

In 1988 the same setup was used for the particle separator flow field calibration test. The test utilized DARE 6 as the digitizing system. DARE 6 provides a higher sampling throughput than DARE 5. The higher throughput allowed NAVSWC to sample the analog signals at a rate of 1,066,000 samples per second and thus a folding frequency 533,000 Hz. Although the sampling rate had been increased by the increase

in DARE sampling rate, DARE 6 being faster than DARE 5, the resolvable bandwidth of signals remained 0 Hz to 80 KHz due to the low pass filter of the Honeywell 101.

Although the process of Figure 2 performs the acquisition of transient signals, it does have significant drawbacks. First, the Honeywell 101 and the DARE system each require an operator. Second, the DARE system must be used to digitize the Honeywell data after a wind tunnel run. The digitizing process requires two operators and both data systems. Preparation for the succeeding wind tunnel run can not proceed until the DARE system is available because it is used to troubleshoot problem gauges. Therefore, digitizing Honeywell 101 data with the DARE system leads to a reduction of wind tunnel productivity. Other problems such as Honeywell 101 noise, data reduction peculiarities, and system complexity also lend to the reasoning that the use of the Honeywell 101 is unsatisfactory. Accordingly, the system of Figure 2 was replaced by the HSDARE.

Architectures

Over the past 10 years data acquisition architecture has evolved with the appearance of more advanced and less expensive technology. In the early 1980's amplifiers and analog to digital converters were expensive. The systems of that

Figure 3 Early 1980s Data Acquisition Architecture

era utilized two levels of multiplexing to achieve a low cost solution to multi channel data acquisition. Figure 3 shows the schematic of such an architecture.

The sensor inputs were multiplexed to the amplifiers, and the amplifier outputs were multiplexed to the analog to digital converter. Data from the analog to digital converter would be stored in a large common memory buffer. The two levels of multiplexing were required due to the high cost of instrumentation amplifiers and analog to digital converters. DARE 5 utilized the architecture of Figure 3. Since each level of multiplexing slows down the throughput of an individual channel this architecture is not useful for transient signal data acquisition without incorporating a setup such as that shown in Figure 2.

Figure 4 Mid 1980s Data Acquisition Architecture.

By the mid 1980's the instrumentation amplifiers had become less expensive. Consequently, systems of that era contained one less level of multiplexing. The architecture that evolved is shown in Figure 4. DARE 6 and DARE 8 employ this type of architecture. Only the A/D converter is multiplexed. Data digitized by the A/D converter are stored in a common memory

within a control computer. This architecture is inherently faster than that of the DARE 5 architecture (Figure 3) if the muxes, amplifiers, and A/D of each architecture switch at equivalent speeds. The speed is limited only by the throughput of the analog to digital converter and by the speed of data storage in the control computer's memory buffer. No time is lost switching inputs between available amplifiers since each input has its own dedicated amplifier.

In the late 1980's the price of analog to digital converters and memory fell to the point that all levels of multiplexing could be removed in a cost effective manner. A sensor's input no longer had to share resources in order to be recorded. Figure 5 shows a block diagram of such an architecture. As can be seen, each sensor has its own mini data acquisition system. Each mini system consists of an A/D converter, a programmable amplifier, and memory to store the digitized data.

Figure 5 1990s Data Acquisition Architecture

The Figure 5 architecture provides more than just distributed data acquisition. It allows faster data acquisition than the other two architectures. It does not require a real time link to a control computer for data storage. Each

sensor can be sampled at a different rate than the other sensors, and the hardware does not have a critical element such as a common A/D. Overall, the Figure 5 system provides many benefits that the Figures 3 & 4 systems do not.

The New System

The HSDARE was procured from Pacific Instruments, Inc. of Concord, CA in October of 1989. Pacific specializes in the manufacture of ruggedized data acquisition systems and transient recorders. Their products have been used in nuclear blast testing facilities and automobile crash test facilities as well as in aerospace facilities. The HSDARE is a laboratory version of the ruggedized systems that Pacific sells. It employs an architecture such as that seen in Figure 5.

The HSDARE consists of twenty transient data recorders (TDRs), twenty programmable amplifiers, a MicroVAX II control computer, software for real time data display and control, an IEEE-488 interface to the TDRs, and several I/O subsystems. All operate together to perform the transient data acquisition function of the Tunnel 9 data acquisition facility.

The HSDARE has a Figure 5 architecture and is actually 20 mini data systems (channels) working in conjunction with each other. Each channel consists of a TDR and a programmable amplifier. The channels are connected together via an IEEE-488 communications link. The communications link master is a MicroVAX II. It provides the user interface and drives setup and control information to each channel over the communications link. The TDRs perform real time data acquisition and data storage. After data are acquired the MicroVAX extracts the data from the TDR memory so that the user can manipulate the data.

Since the architecture is distributed, each channel may be programmed to operate uniquely. That is, each channel (mini system) may acquire data at a different speed from the others, start at a different time, and store a different amount of data. The distributed architecture also lends itself to a failure resiliency. Since the channels do not have a critical central element, component failure tends to be less damaging to the whole transient acquisition system. For example, a single analog to digital converter failure causes only a single channel to be unusable. The Figure 3 and 4 architectures would grind to a halt if a single

analog to digital converter failed. In Tunnel #9 testing all of the channels are triggered at the same time and maintain identical sampling profiles.

Transient Data Recorders

Figure 6 shows a diagram of a transient data recorder (TDR). The HSDARE contains twenty TDRs. Each TDR consists of a 12 bit analog to digital converter, one megasample of memory, control logic, and I/O interfaces to a programmable amplifier and to the control computer. The TDR functions as the digitizer and real time storage subsystem for the analog signals that the amplifier provides.

The TDRs are capable of recording data at speeds ranging from 33 samples per second up to a maximum rate of 1,000,000 samples per second. At 1,000,000 samples per second each TDR can record and store one second's worth of data. The data storage memory is 1 million samples in size (2 Megabytes).

Figure 6 TDR Block Diagram.

The memory is arranged into 16 logical segments. The user allocates the segments as either pre trigger or post trigger segments via the control computer software. Each post trigger segment may sample the data at a different rate than the other post trigger segments. Each pre trigger segment must be setup to sample the data at the same rate as each other pre trigger segment in the particular TDR. This allows the capability to turn up the sampling speed "on the

fly" for signals which fluctuate between steady state and transient.

Data recording by the TDRs is initiated in one of three ways. First, the operator can start the recording via operator console keystroke. Second, the operator can set levels of signals which will trigger the TDRs. Third, an external start signal hardwired into the TDR chassis can initiate data recording. In any case, either type of start signal to a rack of TDRs causes all of the TDRs in the rack to simultaneously begin data acquisition. The termination of recording may occur at differing times for each TDR due to the ability to program different sampling speed profiles for each segment of TDR memory.

Appendix A contains a complete listing of the operating characteristics of the TDRs. Some of the more commonly cited specifications include:

- Sample Speed 33 to 1,000,000 Samp/Sec
- Sample Size 16 bits
- Sample Resolution 12 bits
- +/- 10 Volt Full Scale A/D

Model 9250 Programmable
Pre Amplifiers

Figure 7 shows a block diagram of the model 9250 programmable pre amplifiers. Each 9250 is coupled with a TDR to comprise a channel of the HSDARE system. The 9250's are rack mounted ten to a rack just as are the TDRs and require the same physical amount of space. They communicate with the control computer via the same IEEE-488 communication link that the TDRs utilize.

Each 9250 contains 9 filter frequencies, 10 gains, control circuitry, signal conditioning, and I/O interfaces to the TDR, front panel, and to an optional analog tape subsystem. The 9250s receive setup information via the IEEE control bus from the MicroVAX II. The control information indicates to the amplifier how to configure itself. The control circuitry of the amplifier stores the information in non volatile memory and can supply the setup information to the control computer for verification purposes.

Each 9250 contains nine six pole low pass Butterworth analog filters. Eight of the filters are active, and the ninth is wideband. The eight active frequencies are 10Hz, 50Hz, 100Hz, 500Hz, 1KHz, 10KHz, 25KHz, and 40KHz. The bandwidth of the 9250 is 100KHz and, thus, the signals

passing through the wideband filter are only valid to 100KHz.

Figure 7 Model 9250 Programmable Amplifier

Each amplifier contains signal conditioning in the form of automatic balancing, voltage calibration, shunt calibration, and zero calibration. In Tunnel 9 a dynamic calibration is performed on pressure transducers, and transfer functions are used to determine temperature from thermocouples. The HSDARE utilizes the zero and voltage calibrations to account for amplifier non linearity and offset drift for the temperature gauges. The dynamic pressure calibration is performed by recording data at known test cell pressures. Once several points have been recorded, a slope and intercept are calculated from the data. The typical shunt calibration of pressure transducers is not performed although the option does exist. Other types of gauges are calibrated in a similar fashion.

As seen in Figure 7, the analog signal enters the 9250 and is differentially amplified. Next it passes through a low pass filter and is provided to two outputs. The outputs are to the TDR and to an analog tape recorder. An analog tape output is provided so that the signal to the TDR is not affected by tape recorder anomalies. Both outputs have an impedance less than 1 ohm. Overload is detected on the output line and is used to latch a front panel overload indicator.

Appendix B contains a complete list of 9250 amplifier specifications. Some of the more frequently referenced specifications are:

- Bandwidth 100KHz at 3dB.
- Gains 1, 2, 5, 10, 20, 50, 100, 200, 500, 1000.
- Filters 10, 50, 100, 500, 1K, 10K, 25K, 40KHz.
- Filter Type 6 Pole Low Pass Butterworth
- Input Impedance > 50Mohm.

The Control Computer

Figure 8 shows a block diagram of the control computer. The control computer is a MicroVAX II. The peripheral units attached to the MicroVAX include an LN03 laser printer, VT240 color graphics terminal, two RD54 159 Mbyte Winchester disk drives, three RA60 205 Mbyte removable disk drives, a TK50 tape drive, an Ethernet interface, and an IEEE-488 interface.

Figure 8 HSDARE Control Computer

The system software is written in FORTRAN, and the source code was provided as part of the original purchase agreement. System operation is achieved via menu selections. An ASCII pseudo real time display is provided for

system monitoring, and a RETOS graphics package is used to provide color graphics post processing of the data. All functions of the system setup and operation can be performed via the system software.

The system was delivered as a turn key system with the thought that the system software would be modified in house to provide a better integration into the Tunnel 9 data acquisition facility. Some of the initial in house modifications have targeted the setup and control of the TDRs, the post processing package, and the acquisition of small static tares of data such as those required for test cell type pressure transducer calibration. At this point, some of the software modifications have been completed and others have been started.

Further control computer modifications will target the IEEE-488 interface. The interface, although highly standardized and functional, is slow and requires approximately 45 minutes to archive TDR data from all 20 TDRs to a TK50 tape. The TK50 interface also contributes to the slow data transfer problem. The intent of future upgrades will be to replace the IEEE-488 interface with a faster parallel DMA transfer capability and the TK50 with a 9 track drive. It is estimated that the two changes will provide for data transfer at up to 4 times the speed of the current transfer. Yet another upgrade will take the DMA interface and locate it inside of a dedicated work station which will function as the control station for DARE 6, DARE 8, and HSDARE. This upgrade will replace aging DEC based systems (DARE 8 and DARE 6 utilize PDP-11 control computers) with a more standard and easily upgraded UNIX based work station.

Conclusion

A new high speed data acquisition system has been procured, installed, and integrated into the NAVSWC Hypervelocity Wind Tunnel #9 data acquisition facility. It functions as the transient recording system and off loads the responsibility for recording transients from the Honeywell 101/DARE system configuration. The HSDARE samples data at speeds up to 1 million samples per second per channel and passes signals with bandwidths up to 100KHz. The system is available for use now. It will be upgraded over the next few years with more channels, faster data transfer, and better control computer characteristics. It will become more closely

coupled with the DARE 8 and DARE 6 systems through a common control center, and will carry the responsibility of transient data acquisition.

APPENDIX A TRANSIENT DATA RECORDER SPECIFICATIONS.

Sample Speeds: 33 to 1,000,000 Samples per Second.

Sample Size: Storage 2 Bytes (16 bits).

Sample Resolution: 12 bits (+/- 2048 counts)

A/D Input: +/- 10 Volts.

Memory Size: 1,048,576 Data Points (2,097,152 bytes).

Input Impedance: 10Mohm.

Max Input: +/- 50 Volt.

Bandwidth: 200KHz at 3dB.

Slew Rate: Better than 10 Volts/uSec.

Aperture Uncertainty: Less than .03 nSec.

Droop Rate: Less than .01 percent per second.

Segmented Memory: 16 Segments.

Sample to Sample Uncertainty: Less than .03 nSec One Channel. Less than 50 nSec chan to chan.

APPENDIX B MODEL 9250 AMPLIFIER SPECIFICATIONS

Type: Differential.

Gains: 1, 2, 5, 10, 20, 50, 100, 200, 500, 1000.

Gain Step Accuracy: $\pm 0.1\%$ with Linearity $\pm 0.02\%$ and Stability $\pm 0.02\%$.

Input Impedance: Greater than 50 Mohm.

Common Mode Rejection: 120 dB DC to 60 Hz for High Gains.

Common Mode Rejection: 63 dB + Gain in dB for Lower Gains.

Filter Type: Butterworth 6 Pole Low Pass.

Filter Frequency: 10, 50, 100, 500, 1K, 10K, 25K, 40K, Wideband.

Zero Stability: $\pm 5\mu\text{V}$ RTI and $\pm 0.5\text{mV}$ RTO.

Zero Drift: less than $\pm 1\text{mV}$ for all Gains and Filter Combinations.

Noise: 0.1 Hz to 10 Hz less than 1 μV RTI plus 0.5 mV RTO.

Noise: 0.1 Hz to 100 KHz less than 7 μV RTI plus 0.5 mV RTO.

Linearity: Better than 0.1% of Full Scale.

Bandwidth: 100 KHz.